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Research Article

**THE ROLE OF EXTENDED-SPECTRUM BETA-LACTAMASE
PRODUCING ORGANISMS CAUSING URINARY TRACT
INFECTION IS A RISK FACTOR FOR ACUTE KIDNEY
INJURY AMONG TYPE 2 DIABETIC PATIENTS**Matiullah Alam¹, MD Sakil², Manoj Kumar Yadav³^{1,2,3}Jalalabad Ragib-Rabeya Medical College & Hospital, Bangladesh.

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Abstract:

Background: Urinary tract infection (UTI) is common, and diabetic patients are at increased risk of UTI. A UTI can be complicated by acute kidney injury (AKI). This study was designed to assess whether UTI induced by microorganisms producing extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) should be considered a risk factor for AKI in patients with type 2 diabetes.

Methods: This case-control study was conducted at the Internal Medicine and Nephrology of Jalalabad Ragib Rabeya Medical College and Hospital, Bangladesh for one-year duration from June 2019 to June 2020. Type 2 diabetes patients with culture-confirmed UTIs were assessed. Patients with UTI complicated by AKI were cases and those without AKI were treated as controls. The positivity of the isolated organisms to ESBL was assessed as a risk factor for AKI.

Results: During the study period, a total of 131 patients with type 2 diabetes (male to female ratio 1: 2.6) with inoculated UTIs were enrolled. The mean age and duration of diabetes were 56.1 ± 13.3 and 8.7 ± 5.4 years, respectively. The most common etiological factor was *Escherichia coli* (82, 62.6%), followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (14, 10.7%). Two-thirds (55/82, 67.1%) of *E. coli* and two-fifths (6/14, 42.9%) of *Klebsiella* were ESBL-positive. UTIs in 64 (48.9%) patients were caused by ESBL-positive microorganisms. Of 131 patients with a UTI, 62 (47.3%) had AKI; 40 (40/64, 62.5%) among ESBL-positive organisms and 22 (22/67, 32.8%) among non-ESBL organisms. There was no significant difference in age ($p = 0.71$), gender ($p = 0.26$), diabetes duration ($p = 0.37$) and glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) ($p = 0.69$) between patients and a control group. The positivity of ESBL appeared as a significant risk factor for AKI among the respondents (OR = 3.4, 95% CI = 1.66-6.99, $p = 0.008$).

Conclusions: Almost half of the type 2 diabetic patients with UTI in this study had ESBL-positive microorganisms as etiological factors. UTIs caused by ESBL-positive organisms were a significant risk factor for AKI. Key words: Acute kidney injury, broad spectrum beta-lactamase, risk factor, type 2 diabetes, urinary tract infection.

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INTRODUCTION:

A urinary tract infection (UTI) is one of the most common bacterial infections in adults. Women and patients with diabetes are more likely to develop UTIs [1-2]. *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* are the two most common organisms responsible for UTIs worldwide [3-4]. Expanded spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) producing strains are an increasing problem, and patients with long-term diabetes and poor glycemic control are at increased risk of UTIs due to ESBL-positive microbes [5-6]. A UTI can be complicated by acute kidney injury (AKI) and sepsis⁷. This study was designed to assess whether UTIs caused by ESBL-positive microorganisms should be considered a risk factor for AKI in patients with type 2 diabetes.

METHODS:

This case-control study was conducted at the Internal Medicine and Nephrology of Jalalabad Ragib Rabeya Medical College and Hospital, Bangladesh for one-year duration from June 2019 to June 2020. Patients hospitalized with clinical diagnosis of UTI were initially included in the study. The clean catch technique was used to collect urine (preferably in the early morning from the midstream). The collected samples were sent to the microbiology laboratory within half an hour, where they were inoculated on Mac Conkey agar and blood agar within two hours. Significant positives from the culture (semi-quantitative colony count > 1x10⁵ colony forming units / ml) were then included for the study. Catheterized patients, pregnant women, patients with insufficient / no growth or growth of *Candida* in urine

cultures were excluded from the study. Organism growth was further assessed by colony characteristics and biochemical tests including triple ferric sugar (TSI), indole urea mobility (MIU), and Simon's citrate. Selected samples were then subculture for antibiotic susceptibility in Mueller-Hilton (MH) agar using a Kibra-Bauer disc susceptibility test. A positive ESBL result was phenotypically determined using the Double Disc Synergy test. In addition to the culture of urine, the patients were assessed clinically and with other required laboratory tests. It is reported whether patients have developed AKI. AKI was diagnosed according to the clinical practice guidelines for kidney disease: improvement in global outcomes (KDIGO). Subsequently, patients with UTI complicated by AKI were considered cases and UTI cases without AKI as controls. Finally, ESBL-positive organisms were assessed as a risk factor for AKI among study participants. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 20.0 was used for data analysis. A p value of <0.05 was considered significant. The results are presented in the tables.

RESULTS:

During the study period, a total of 131 patients with type 2 diabetes, including 95 women, with UTI confirmed by culture were enrolled. The mean age and duration of the subjects' diabetes were 56.07 ± 13.30 and 8.70 ± 5.39 years, respectively. Sixty-two (47.3%) of UTI patients were complicated by AKI (cases). There was no significant difference in age, sex, duration, and control of diabetes between patients and controls (Table I).

Base-line characteristics of the study subjects (N=131)

Characteristics	Overall (N=131)	Cases (UTI with AKI) (n=62)	Controls (UTI without AKI) (n=69)	p value
Mean age (years)	56.07±13.30	55.61±14.13	56.48±12.59	0.71
Male: Female	01:02.6	20:42	16:53	0.246
Mean duration of DM (years)	8.70±5.39	9.15±5.40	8.30±5.39	0.3696
Mean HbA1c (%)	8.93±1.96	9.0±1.78	8.86±2.13	0.6857

The most common etiological factor was *E. coli* (82, 62.6%), followed by *Klebsiella* (14, 10.7%). Two thirds (55/82, 67.1%) of *E. coli* and two fifths (6/14, 42.9%) of *Klebsiella* were ESBL-positive (Table II). Etiological agents among the study subjects (N=131)

Bacteria	ESBL-positive	Non-ESBL	Total
E. coli	55 (42.0)	27 (20.6)	82 (62.6)
K. pneumoniae	6 (4.6)	8 (6.1)	14 (10.7)
Pseudomonas spp.	---	3 (2.3)	3 (2.3)
Citrobacter	---	3 (2.3)	3 (2.3)
Staphylococcus	---	7 (5.3)	7 (5.3)
*MRSA Staph	---	1 (0.8)	1 (0.8)
Enterococcus	---	10 (7.6)	10 (7.6)
Acinetobacter	---	6 (4.6)	6 (4.6)
Citrobacter	1 (0.8)	---	0.8)
Streptococcus	--2 (1.5)	2 (1.5)	1.5)
Enterobacter	64 (48.9)	---	2 (1.5)
Total		67 (51.1)	131 (100)

UTIs in 64 (48.9%) patients were caused by ESBL-positive microorganisms. Of 131 patients with a UTI, 62 (47.3%) had AKI; 40 (40/64, 62.5%) among ESBL-positive organisms and 22 (22/67, 32.8%) among non-ESBL organisms. The positivity of ESBL turned out to be an important risk factor for AKI among the respondents (Table III).

Evaluation of UTI with ESBL-positive organisms as risk-factor for AKI among the study subjects (N=131)

Bacteria	ESBL positive	Non ESBL	Total
ESBL-positive (64)	40	24	3.4,
Non-ESBL (67)	22	45	1.66-6.99, 0.008

DISCUSSION:

The definition of AKI has evolved at various stages, and KDIGO has defined AKI as having one or more of the following 3 criteria: absolute increase in serum creatinine of more than 0.3 mg / dL over a 48-hour period, increase in serum creatinine to 1.5 baseline times within one week and reduction of urine production to less than 0.5 ml / kg / hour for more than 6 hours [9-10]. This is the most recent and widely used AKI criterion and we used this definition in our study to define AKI. We mainly relied on the first two criteria based on serum creatinine values. AKI is common in hospital settings and more often in intensive care units (ICUs). Diabetic patients are also at increased risk of AKI. AKI and CKD histories are reported risk factors for AKI [11-12]. UTI can be complicated by AKI. Older age, diabetes, upper UTIs, and poor baseline renal function are reported risk factors for developing AKI in a UTI. In our study, we assessed a positive ESBL of UTI-causing organisms as a risk factor for AKI. ESBL-positive UTIs are increasingly reported in Bangladesh, and Rahim MA *et al.* Report that women with long-term diabetes and poor glycemic control are risk factors for ESBL-

positive UTIs. A similar observation has been reported in other studies [13]. In another study, prior hospitalization and multiple UTIs and antibiotic use were risk factors for UTIs caused by ESBL-positive microorganisms. UTIs caused by ESBL-positive microorganisms can also worsen renal function in transplant recipients. We found that a positive ESBL result is a significant risk factor for AKI in patients with type 2 diabetes. This study had some potential limitations [14]. It was a single-center study, the study period was only 3 months, and the sample size was small. We did not assess other risk factors for AKI such as basal renal function, concomitant treatment with angiotensin blockers such as angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors (ACEI) or angiotensin receptor blockers (ARB), the hydration status of patients as vomiting is a common feature of UTIs and whether patients have been treated any antibiotic with nephrotoxic potential such as aminoglycosides. Given all of these confounding factors, a larger, multicenter study will provide a more reliable answer to the research question tested in this study. Diabetes mellitus with UTI complicated by AKI deserved long-term follow-up of final renal outcomes, and it was

beyond our scope for this particular study to include this fact as well [15].

CONCLUSIONS:

In conclusion, it can be said that ESBL-positive UTIs are increasing; in this study, nearly half of the patients with type 2 diabetes had an ESBL-positive UTI. UTI induced by ESBL-positive uropathogens has been shown to be a significant risk factor for AKI in patients with type 2 diabetes. Good glycemic control and general measures to prevent UTIs may be helpful in preventing ESBL-positive UTIs and thus reducing the risk of AKI in patients with type 2 diabetes.

REFERENCES:

1. Bielen L, Likic R. Experience with fosfomycin in the treatment of complicated urinary tract infections caused by extended-spectrum beta-lactamase-producing Enterobacteriaceae. *Therapeutic advances in infectious disease*. 2019 Jun;6:2049936119858883.
2. Goyal D, Dean N, Neill S, Jones P, Dascomb K. Risk factors for community-acquired extended-spectrum beta-lactamase-producing Enterobacteriaceae infections—A retrospective study of symptomatic urinary tract infections. *In Open forum infectious diseases* 2019 Feb (Vol. 6, No. 2, p. ofy357). US: Oxford University Press.
3. Bekoe A, Azorliade R, Ablordey A, Addo MG. Antibiotic resistance and genotypic detection of extended spectrum beta-lactamase producing pathogens in catheter associated urinary tract infection at a teaching facility in Kumasi, Ghana. *African Journal of Microbiology Research*. 2020 Aug 31;14(8):395-401.
4. Grosen AK, Povlsen JV, Lemming LE, Jørgensen SM, Dahlerup JF, Hvas CL. Faecal microbiota transplantation eradicated extended-spectrum beta-lactamase-producing *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from a renal transplant recipient with recurrent urinary tract infections. *Case Reports in Nephrology and Dialysis*. 2019;9(2):102-7.
5. Mansouri F, Sheibani H, Javedani Masroor M, Afsharian M. Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL)-producing Enterobacteriaceae and urinary tract infections in pregnant/postpartum women: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *International Journal of Clinical Practice*. 2019 Dec;73(12):e13422.
6. Al-Tamimi M, Abu-Raideh J, Albalawi H, Shalabi M, Saleh S. Effective oral combination treatment for extended-spectrum beta-lactamase-producing *Escherichia coli*. *Microbial Drug Resistance*. 2019 Oct 1;25(8):1132-41.
7. Koksai E, Tulek N, Sonmezer MC, Temocin F, Bulut C, Hatipoglu C, Erdinc FS, Ertem G. Investigation of risk factors for community-acquired urinary tract infections caused by extended-spectrum beta-lactamase *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella* species. *Investigative and clinical urology*. 2019 Jan 1;60(1):46-53.
8. Rahim MA, Zaman S, Jahan I, Habib SH, Samad T, Chowdhury TA, Saha SK, Latif A, Khoda MM, Billah MM, Ananna MA. Urinary Tract Infection due to Extended-spectrum Beta-lactamase Producing Organisms is a Risk Factor for Bacteraemia Among Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *Bangladesh Journal of Medicine*. 2020;31(1):9-12.
9. Vachvanichsanong P, McNeil EB, Dissaneewate P. Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* urinary tract infections. *Epidemiology & Infection*. 2020 Dec 17:1-21.
10. Tullos JB, Stoudenmire LL, Pouliot JD. Piperacillin-Tazobactam Versus Carbapenems for the Treatment of Nonbacteremic Urinary Tract Infections due to Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamase-Producing Enterobacteriaceae. *Hospital Pharmacy*. 2020 Feb;55(1):44-9.
11. Ohnishi T, Mishima Y, Takizawa S, Tsutsumi K, Amemiya A, Akiyama N, Kanna Y, Asato S, Tomita M, Ikemiyagi M, Shikoro N. Clinical Features of Febrile Urinary Tract Infection Caused by Extended-spectrum Beta-lactamase-producing *Escherichia Coli* in Children. *The Keio Journal of Medicine*. 2019.
12. Ugbo EN, Anyamene CO, Moses IB, Iroha IR, Babalola OO, Ukpai EG, Chukwunwejim CR, Egbule CU, Emioye AA, Okata-Nwali OD, Igwe OF. Prevalence of blaTEM, blaSHV, and blaCTX-M genes among extended spectrum beta-lactamase-producing *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* of clinical origin. *Gene Reports*. 2020 Dec 1;21:100909.
13. Moges F, Eshetie S, Abebe W, Mekonnen F, Dagne M, Endale A, Amare A, Feleke T, Gizachew M, Tiruneh M. High prevalence of extended-spectrum beta-lactamase-producing Gram-negative pathogens from patients attending Felege Hiwot Comprehensive Specialized Hospital, Bahir Dar, Amhara region. *PloS one*. 2019 Apr 15;14(4):e0215177.
14. Majeed HT, Aljanaby AA. Antibiotic susceptibility patterns and prevalence of some extended spectrum beta-lactamases genes in gram-negative bacteria isolated from patients infected with urinary tract infections in Al-Najaf

- City, Iraq. Avicenna journal of medical biotechnology. 2019 Apr;11(2):192.
15. Xiao T, Yang K, Zhou Y, Zhang S, Ji J, Ying C, Shen P, Xiao Y. Risk factors and outcomes in non-transplant patients with extended-spectrum beta-lactamase-producing *Escherichia coli* bacteremia: a retrospective study from 2013 to 2016. *Antimicrobial Resistance & Infection Control*. 2019 Dec 1;8(1):144.